

The Position Of Women In Islam And The Ancient Civilization

Nayab Gul, Anwarullah, Sarfraz Ali, HM Azhar Usama, Hafiz Muhammad Hamid

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Abstract

This article presents a broad panorama on the position and status of women in various religions as a research and analytical review and a large body of discussion on various aspects arising from it. The style of this research paper will be narrative. A review of the literature has revealed that the fragile gender with its many gifted talents suffers from discrimination all over the world. Women struggling for their rights, even in the 21st century, seem unable to achieve the standard of their greatness that nature has bestowed upon them. International Women's Day is celebrated on March 8 to highlight the struggle of women to achieve the same rights. Women are an integral part of the universe. Mother, sister, daughter and wife are a precious gift of God in every form. Even the daughter has been described as the mercy of God, but regardless of the universal teachings of the Quran and Hadith, women have been discriminated against in every era and every society. Below we see the standard of sanctity and dignity of women in different religions: Before Islam, the overall social condition in the religions was very bad. For a long time in Rome, women were legally in a very low position, father and husband were their masters. Morale was very bad. At that time, prostitution was done in public. Brothels were common. The husband was possessed to the extent that he could kill his wife. In the eyes of the law, women were considered weak-minded. He had no rights whatsoever.

Introduction

Religions treatment of women is polite and respectful, benevolent, wise and respectful. It is in favor of both men and women. In relation to both men and women, the society takes a realistic approach to all creatures and is in harmony with the real and basic needs, temperament and nature. That is, no one expects from anyone more than the strength and energy and more than the resources given to him. To understand the Islamic perspective on women, it can be examined from three angles. First: His role in the path of spiritual and spiritual perfection as a human being; From this point of view, there is no difference between men and women. Just as there have been many great men in history, there have also been many great and distinguished women. II: Social, political, academic and economic activities; From the point of view of Islam, the door of academic, economic and political activity and activities is completely open for women. If someone is trying to deprive women from academic activities by referring to the Islamic point of view, is trying to keep them away from economic activities or is insisting on not having anything to do with political and social affairs, then it is actually God's command. Acting contrary. Women can perform activities as far as their needs and requirements and physical energy allows. As much as possible, they should do political, economic and social affairs, it is not prohibited in Islamic Sharia. However, since a woman is more fragile than a man in terms of physical structure, she has some requirements of her own. Imposing forceful work on a woman is abuse, Islam does not advise it at all. However, he has not stopped (the woman). Hazrat Ameer al-Mu'minin (peace be upon him) is reported to have said: Al-MaraaatRayhanawalisteBakharmanat means a woman is like a flower, not a Kaharman. Kaharman means Honorable Presenter and Servant. You address men and say: Women are like flowers in your homes, treat them with great delicacy and attention. A woman is not your servant and servant for you to put hard and powerful work on her head. This is very important.

❖ STATUS OF WOMEN IN DIFFERENT RELIGIONS

Religion is an important social institution, which plays an important role in the formation of human society. Its principles and ideas determine the values for the society. It also determines the position and rank. ⁽¹⁾ The views presented by different religions about men and women in the world have a direct impact on their social life in different nations. The education that continued to reach 'gradually, it started to be taken to mean that the relationship with a woman brings one closer to sin, so it should be shunned. As this concept was strengthened, hatred towards women increased. ⁽¹⁾

❖ JUDAISM

According to Jewish traditions, woman is an impure being, and the trouble in this universe is due to her. According to them, men are good natured and have good character, and women are evil and deceitful, because she seduced Adam to eat the fruit from which Allah What was forbidden?

In the Jewish law, the authority of the man and the subjugation of the woman are prominent. A woman did not have the right to marry again. ⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾

In addition to family life, women were also deprived of rights such as will, testimony and inheritance. According to Jewish law, in the presence of a male heir, a woman was deprived of inheritance. According to their laws, the daughter's position in inheritance comes after the grandsons. If there is no son of the deceased, the inheritance goes to the grandson, and if there is no grandson, then the inheritance goes to the daughter. ^(iv)

❖ CHRISTIANITY

Christianity has the same view of women that we see in Judaism. The basic idea of Christianity was that woman is the mother of sin and the root of evil and the door to hell.

Tertullian, one of the early Christian imams, had these views on women:

"She is the gate of the devil," the tree leading to the forbidden, "breaking God's law and robbing the man of God's image" ^(v).

The Cry So System, who is considered a great Christian imam, says about the woman:

"Woman is 'an inevitable evil', an innate temptation, 'a desirable calamity', 'a personal danger', 'a plundering round', 'a bejeweled affliction.'" ^(vi)

Shah Moinuddin Nadvi sheds light on the status of women in Christianity:

"Woman was considered to be a source of temptation and evil. Abeds and ascetics used to run away from her shadow. Great monks considered it a sin to meet their mother and look at her face." The history of monasticism is full of misogyny. ^(vii)

Dr. Khalid Alvi writes:

"Since in Christian ethics, celibacy and avoidance of sexual relations was the real perfection, therefore marriage and sexual relations themselves were impure and untouchable. It was declared as a source of sin. In all the laws made in the Christian Sharia, an attempt was made to keep the status of women low. Her rights in inheritance and property were limited. She did not even have authority over her own earnings. Divorce and divorce were not allowed. The domestic laws of the Christian world were strict, as if the Christian religion tried to humiliate the woman and keep her bound in restrictions. There was nothing but a toy in hand. ^(viii)

❖ HINDUISM

In Hindu dharma, woman is described as a collection of rebellious qualities, 'mischievous', seducer of men, 'false, cunning', stupid and cruel. Woman is included in the category of Shudras and along with them, she is also described as 'papayani' i.e. sinner. That she is a born sinner and her place in life is fixed. In the theory of Hinduism, there is no mention of the woman's personality as a whole. To give birth to a son 'The appropriate role for a woman only emerges as a wife and mother.' ^(ix)

Like the Jews and Greeks, Hindus considered women to be the root of sin and the source of suffering and refused to recognize her permanent status. According to Hindu religion, there is no worship for a married woman, she should serve and serve her husband, this is the greatest worship. According to Manu, since women become half of a man after marriage, it is papa for them to perform separate yagya and beret, they should only serve their husbands ^(x).

In Hinduism, there is an abominable and abominable method of "nayog" for obtaining children. If the husband is unable to bear children, he can force his wife to marry another man so that he can have children ^(xi).

❖ BUDDHISM

Buddhism is considered as a 'modern religion'. Despite this, he also declared women impure. We find proof of this in the teachings of Gautama Buddha. Gautama Buddha said to his followers that if you want to be saved, ^(xii) you should break the relationship with your women and first of all he broke the relationship with his women. ^(xiii)

According to Dr. Amina Tahsin, women were always considered lower than men in terms of rank in Buddhism, but compared to Hinduism, women enjoyed social and religious freedom in Buddhism. ^(xiv)

❖ JAINISM

According to Jainism, women are devoid of goodness and the root of all evil and negativity. Therefore, this religion encourages men not to develop any kind of relationship with women. Neither look at women nor talk to them. ^(xv)

In Jainism, although unlike Hinduism, women have religious rights, but it encourages women and men to lead a monastic life. In Jainism, polygamy is prohibited and widows are not allowed to remarry. ^(xvi)

❖ STATUS OF WOMEN IN ISLAMIC CULTURE

When the intellectual field of the world is reviewed and then the Islamic point of view is examined, it is clearly felt that the human society can reach the desired destination and direction in relation to the relationship between men and women only when the Islamic Ideas should be understood and understood without any reduction or exaggeration and try to present them. At present, the behavior that has been adopted in relation to women in

materialistic civilizations and that is going on is not acceptable in any case and it is not in the interest and right of the woman and not in the benefit of the society.

Islam wishes that the intellectual, academic, political, social and above all spiritual and spiritual development of women reach their goal of perfection and their existence as an important member of human society and family is the final limit. May it be fruitful and useful. This is the basis of all Islamic teachings, including the issue of hijab. In the Holy Qur'an, when Allah wants to give examples of good and bad people, He chooses a woman in relation to both. One example is the wife of Pharaoh and the other example is the wives of Prophet Noah and Prophet Lot. And Zarb Allah, for example, for those who believe, Pharaoh presents the wives of Hazrat Noah and Hazrat Lot as an example of a person who is evil, unlucky, deviant and growing in the wrong direction. Here the question arises that men were also there, one example would have been given by a man and one example would have been given by a woman. But no, in the entire Qur'an, whenever it is said that ZarbullahlazinAminwa or ZarbullahlazinKufrwa, both examples are presented through women.

❖ THE BEHAVIOR OF ISLAM IN RELATION TO WOMEN

The treatment of women in Islam and the Islamic democratic system is polite and respectful, benevolent, wise and respectful. It is in favor of both men and women. Islam, in relation to both men and women, similarly, in relation to all creatures, adopts a realistic and real and basic needs, temperament and nature compatible approach. That is, no one expects from anyone more than the strength and energy and more than the resources given to him. To understand the Islamic perspective on women, it can be examined from three angles.

- His role in the path of spiritual and spiritual perfection as a human being; From this point of view, there is no difference between men and women. Just as there have been many great men in history, there have also been many great and distinguished women.
- Social, political, academic and economic activities; From the point of view of Islam, the door of academic, economic and political activity and activities is completely open for women. If someone is trying to deprive women from academic activities by referring to the Islamic point of view, is trying to keep them away from economic activities or is insisting on not having anything to do with political and social affairs, then it is actually God's command. Acting contrary. Women can perform activities as far as their needs and requirements and physical energy allows. As much as possible, they should do political, economic and social affairs, it is not prohibited in Islamic Sharia. However, since a woman is more fragile than a man in terms of physical structure, she has some requirements of her own. Imposing forceful work on a woman is abuse, Islam does not advise it at all. However, he has not stopped (the woman). It is narrated from HazratAmeerul Momineen (peace be upon him) that he says:

Al-Maraat Rehana Wa List Bakhramanat means a woman is like a flower, not a hero.

Kaharman means Honorable Presenter and Servant. You address men and say: Women are like flowers in your homes, treat them with great delicacy and attention. A woman is not your servant and servant for you to put hard and powerful work on her head. This is very important.

The fact that some people make it a condition before marriage that a woman should be employed, have her own income and earnings, is completely wrong. Of course, it is not against the Shariat, but Islam does not advise this at all. Islam has not said anything on the basis of which we should stop women from participating in economic and social activities, but on the other hand, Islam has not said that women are required to be hard-working and powerful, politically, socially and economically. Be engaged in activities. The ideology of Islam is moderate. That is, if a woman has free time, raising children is not hindering her, she has passion and interest and physical strength and energy and she wants to participate in social, political and economic affairs, then there is no harm. Is. But to force him and order him to go and find employment in any way possible and to work enough daily so that you can bear some of the burden of household expenses from this income, is not fair. Islam has never commanded a woman to do this. He calls it a kind of abuse of women.^{xvii}

I would recommend families to give their girls an opportunity to pursue higher education. May no parent stop their daughter from getting higher education in the name of piety! No, religion has never said that. According to religion, there is no difference between boys and girls in terms of education. If a boy gets higher education, a girl can also get higher education. Young girls should get education, set the goals of knowledge, increase knowledge. Be aware of your importance and status and understand your worth, so that they know how hollow and baseless the propaganda of global arrogance is about women. Through education these things can be understood.

- Seeing the woman as a member of the family. It is most important and valuable. In Islam, a man is not allowed to coerce a woman and impose anything on her. Limited rights are reserved for men within the family which is actually very wise. Whoever these rights are presented and explained to, he will support and support it. In the same way, some rights have been reserved for women within the family and there is great expediency hidden in them too. Both men and women have their own specific emotions, moods, morals and desires. If both of them act properly according to their feelings and desires, then a very good harmonious and mutually favorable couple will come into being in the house. If a man abuses, the balance gets disturbed, similarly, if a woman abuses something, the balance also

gets lost. Islam sees man and woman inside the house as the two doors of the door, the two eyes of the face, the two fronts of life and the two co-workers in a shop. Each of them has its own temperament, its own characteristics, its own traits. Physically, spiritually, intellectually, emotionally and emotionally. If these two genders live together observing the limits and standards prescribed by Islam, a strong, kind, blessed and highly efficient family will emerge.

Islam showed those men who used to take their service from women on the basis of their physical or financial strength, often subjected women to humiliation and humiliation, showed their limits and brought women to their true status and some things. He was considered equal to a man. These Muslims and Muslim women and the believers and the believers are Muslim men, Muslim women, worshiping men, worshiping women, men who worship at night and women who pray awake at night. It is known that in Islam all these spiritual and spiritual places and high human levels are equally divided between men and women. In this sense, women are also equal to men. Whoever works for the sake of Allah, male or female, male or female, we will grant him a pure life.^{xviii} In some places, Islam has given priority to women over men. For example, a man and a woman are the parents of a child and this child belongs to both of them, but it is more obligatory for the child to serve the mother. The right of the mother is more on the neck of the children and the duties of the children are more serious in relation to the mother. In response to the question, the Prophet of Islam asked, "Who should I do good and good deeds with?" He has said that Amak means with his mother. You repeated it again and repeated the same phrase a third time. When the questioner asked the same question for the fourth time, he said that Abak means with his father. Therefore, the right of the mother over the children is more in the family and the duties of the children are also more in relation to the mother. However, the reason for this is not that Allah Ta'ala has favored some people over others (for no reason). The reason for this is that women do a lot of hard work. This is the requirement of divine justice. He who has more troubles has more rights. Since (the mother) endures more hardships, her value is also higher.

All this is a requirement of justice. In financial matters, in relation to family rights, in relation to guardianship of the family and in relation to running the affairs of the house, Islam has a very balanced approach. In these matters too, the Islamic law has made such a provision that no one, male or female, should be subjected to the slightest oppression. It has also defined the rights of men and also pointed out the rights of women. One thing is put in the man's veil and another thing is kept in the woman's veil. Those who have insight, if they reflect, they also feel these facts regularly and they have written these things in books.

In the eyes of Islam, gender, i.e., being male or female, is not a subject of discussion, but human evolution has been discussed, human morals have been made a subject of discussion, skills have been developed, duties have been discussed which are related to Can be of any gender. However, familiarity with the mood is necessary for this. Islam recognizes the temperament of both men and women. In the eyes of Islam, the most important thing is the maintenance of balance, that is, the complete observance of justice and fairness between human beings, including men and women. Equality of rights is a topic of discussion. However, it is possible that in some places the rulings in relation to women and men are different. Just as men's and women's temperaments differ in certain characteristics. In Islamic teachings, most of the facts related to men and women can be seen in the natural traits and temperament and psychology.

From the assessment of the position and status of the delicate gender in different nations and religions, it is known that women struggle with the darkness of oppression, oppression, humiliation, abuse, narrow-mindedness and ignorance. Vamudat was blessed with kindness. Islam is the religion of nature; it gives all natural and legitimate rights to women as human beings.

Dr. Obaidullah Fahad Falahi writes:

"The step taken by the Holy Quran in the sixth century AD to eliminate the differences between men and women and treat them with equal respect and dignity was so revolutionary that as a result, The world has changed. In determining the status and status of women, Islam left all other religions behind. Under the shadow of Islam, men's entire perspective and practical attitude towards women changed, and after the Prophet's (PBUH) mission, women created a new history that had never existed before and today's so-called Extinct even in advanced age."^(xix)

Islam has been very lenient towards women; their temperament and their natural weaknesses have been taken into consideration. On various occasions in the Qur'an and Hadith, men have been exhorted to act with forgiveness and gentleness in the case of women, to be considerate of their emotionality, to be considerate of their sensitive and sophisticated nature, and to treat them well. "Be the best in their favor." Even if they are guilty of mistakes, they should be explained gently. "Don't be harsh."

In the Holy Qur'an, men are advised to treat women well:

Be kind to women. If you dislike them (even then avoid them), it may be that the one whom you dislike, may Allah bless him abundantly."^(xx)

The Messenger of Allah, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, said: "The most perfect person in terms of faith is the one whose morals are the best, and the best among you are those who treat their wives."^(xxi)

Men are called "Qawam" in the Holy Qur'an. They are the head of women, their guardians, their protectors, their companions in sorrow, the fulfillment of their needs, and the responsibility of their security. Father, brother, husband, son, are their sponsors in different stages of life, if these are not present, other Mahram relatives like 'grandfather, grandfather, uncle or uncle', however, women are not left helpless in any case.

Although the economic burden is not imposed on the woman, she has full freedom of economic activity. She can play an active and active role in the society, keeping in mind the protection of her chastity and household responsibilities. Sahabiyat was associated with trade, agriculture, herding, handicrafts and tanning, etc.

Hazrat Zainab bintHajjash (may Allah be pleased with her) used to work as a tanner and a seamstress^(xxii).

Hazrat Abdullah's wife Hazrat Zainab asked the Holy Prophet (SAW) "Can I spend my husband's money on the orphans under my care?" He said: "Yes." And in the hadith, 'Your husband and your children are more deserving that you give charity to them'^(xxiii).

The participation of the Sahabiyat in the Ghazwat, the service of the sick and the wounded, and the care of the sick are also mentioned in the hadiths.

Islam gave women a complete legal and moral identity, and determined her scope and field of action. According to Islam, women have a separate legal existence. Therefore, she has legal rights. A woman can have her own personal property and she can own her own property. She has full authority to dispose of the property. Therefore, there is no difference between men and women in terms of general human rights.^(xxiv)

The verse of the Holy Qur'an is a reflection of the fact that Islam considers women as a respectable and reliable being and does not discriminate, yes, keeping in mind the physical nature of women and the protection of her chastity, it mandates certain limits.

"Whoever does a good deed, whether male or female, provided that he is a believer, we will certainly grant him a pure life and reward him for his good deeds."^(xxv)

Conclusions

In ancient societies, a woman's existence was possible only under the domination of a man. Or under the control of her husband or under the control of the factory and farm owner. A woman did not have any rights that women get in a civilized society. He had no right of choice, no property rights and no power of tyranny. Later, women were included in the commercial field and social affairs. The decision to give women ownership rights in Europe, according to the careful analysis of European sociologists themselves, was because factories laid the groundwork for new industry and technology, and they were used by hardworking workers and There was a need for workers but there was a shortage of workers. They were suffering greatly due to shortage of workers. They decided to bring women into the factories and take full advantage of this workforce, by the way, women were given less labor, they announced that women also have ownership rights. In the early 20th century, Europeans gave women ownership rights, but at the same time, they also provided all the equipment for women's pleasure. They left the woman helpless by bringing her into the social flow. It is a cruel and wrong way of thinking and behavior towards women in the West and Europe.

This is not the case in Islam. In Islam, a woman is the owner of her own wealth and assets. Whether the husband likes it or not, the father likes it or not. It doesn't matter. She can freely spend her capital, her goods and the wealth she has accumulated, no one has the right to interrogate her. In terms of supporting women's economic rights, the world is thirteen hundred years behind Islam. Islam did this thirteen hundred years ago.

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Author Information

Nayab Gul

PhD. Scholar, Department of Islamic studies and Arabic, Lahore Garrison University, Lahore, Pakistan

Dr. Anwarullah

Lecturer, Department of Islamic Studies, University of Okara, Okara, Punjab, Pakistan

Sarfraz Ali

PhD Scholar, Department of Islamic Studies, University of Okara, Okara, Punjab, Pakistan

Dr. HM Azhar Usama

Assistant Professor, Department of Islamic Studies, the University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan
(Corresponding Author)

Hafiz Muhammad Hamid

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Islamic Studies, Lahore Garrison University, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan
